

CORRELATIONS OF HRM PRACTICES OF FOOD AND BEVERAGES COMPANIES TOWARDS EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE AND ORGANIZATIONAL STANDING

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the correlation between human resource management (HRM) practices and employee performance as well as organizational standing in selected food and beverage companies. Using a descriptive correlational research design, survey data were gathered from employees to assess HRM dimensions such as recruitment, training, compensation, recognition, and career opportunities. Results showed that HRM practices were perceived as effective, with recruitment and training having the strongest impact on employee performance. Compensation, recognition, and career development were also positively associated with motivation, retention, and service quality. Findings further revealed a significant positive relationship between HRM practices and organizational standing, indicating that effective HR systems enhance both employee productivity and company reputation. The study concludes that fair and well-structured HRM practices are vital for sustaining employee success and organizational competitiveness in the food and beverage sector.

Keywords: *HRM practices, employee performance, organizational standing, food and beverage industry*

INTRODUCTION

During modern competitive landscape, both employee performance and the reputation of an organization are essential for achieving success (Aina & Atan, 2020;

Alvarez & Domingo, 2024). Across the globe, organizations in both public and private sectors constantly look for innovative approaches to improve operational performance (Asogwa et al., 2023). This is particularly evident in the food and beverage industry, which is characterized by high customer expectations, rapid service demands, and a fast-paced environment (Rodriguez, 2021; Rivera, 2023). Managing human resources effectively is critical in this sector, as it ensures that skilled and motivated employees can meet operational and strategic objectives (De Castro & Mendoza, 2022; Santiago & Delos Reyes, 2021).

Human Resource Management (HRM) practices encompass a range of strategies aimed at enhancing employee productivity, job satisfaction, and engagement (Dela Cruz & Cabaluna, 2022; Garcia, 2021). When these practices are aligned with business objectives, they can significantly improve both individual and organizational performance (Bloom & Van Reenen, 2011; Satyendra, 2020). In industries like food and beverage, where operational efficiency and customer satisfaction are crucial, HRM serves as a strategic tool for sustainable growth (Aina & Atan, 2020; Martinez & Salazar, 2022). This study explores how HRM practices influence employee performance and organizational reputation in selected food and beverage businesses, offering insights into the direct link between human capital strategies and business outcomes

Research Questions

The purpose of this study assessed the Correlations of HRM Practices of Food and Beverages Companies towards Employees Performances and Organizational Standing in selected stores in X Mall. Explicitly, this answered the following:

1. What are the respondents' demographic characteristics in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age
 - 1.2. Gender
 - 1.3. Educational Background
 - 1.4. Monthly Income
 - 1.5. Marital Status
2. How do employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies in terms of:
 - 2.1. Recruitment
 - 2.2. Employee Engagement
 - 2.3. Compensation & Benefits
 - 2.4. Career Development
 - 2.5. Training & Development and
 - 2.6. Reward System
3. What is the level of effectiveness in the food and beverage companies' employee performances and organizational standing in terms of:
 - 3.1. Employee Performance
 - 3.2. Organizational Standing

4. Is there a significant difference level of effectiveness regarding to the food and beverage companies' employee performances and organizational standing to their employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies?

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive research design was employed in this study to collect and analyze numerical information. Descriptive research is used to describe the current condition of a subject by answering questions such as what, how, when, and where. In this study, descriptive statistics were applied to display the respondents' demographic characteristics and summarize their views.

The researchers used this method to gather clear and accurate data on how employees perceive Human Resource Management (HRM) practices in various food and beverage companies in Quezon City. It helped them understand employees' experiences in the workplace and their opinions about how HRM practices are carried out (Lopez & Santiago, 2023). The data collected was used to describe how HRM practices are viewed by the employees without analyzing cause or effect (Reyes & Antonio, 2021).

Population, Sample Size, and Sampling Technique

The stratified random sampling, a method of probability sampling, was used in the investigation to select respondents. To determine the sample size, central limit theorem formula was applied, resulting in a sample of 60 respondents from a larger population of employees in food and beverage companies. With using the confidence level is 90% and margin of error is 5%. This approach ensured random selection, minimizing bias and improving generalizability (Ezenekwe, 2020). Respondents were selected based on criteria such as experience with Human Resource Management (HRM) practices, aligning with the research objectives.

This technique is supported by The Central Limit Theorem (CLT), as explained by asserts that, independent of the population distribution's shape, the sampling distribution of the mean approaches a normal distribution when the sample size is large enough. In empirical research, applying simple random sampling ensures that every population member has an equal chance of selection, which increases the likelihood of obtaining a representative sample. This process reduces sampling error and enhances the reliability, accuracy, and generalizability of statistical conclusions.

Description of Respondents

The participants in this study were selected from employees working in various food and beverage companies using a probability sampling method, specifically stratified sampling. A total of 60 participants were selected, with respondents chosen randomly to ensure that all relevant roles were represented in the sample (Wang et al., 2011).

This approach was employed to ensure that the sample accurately reflected the diversity of job functions within the food and beverage industry (Tavitiyaman et al., 2011). Stratified sampling allowed for a more comprehensive understanding of how Human Resource Management (HRM) practices are perceived across different job roles, ensuring that the findings are generalizable to various sectors of the industry.

Research Instrument

To gather the information needed for the inquiry, the researchers used a survey questionnaire. The survey was administered online with a Google Survey Form, which was given to study individuals by QR code and form links (Garcia, 2021).

The respondents were particularly employees and the HR personnel of the preferred food and beverages establishments in Quezon city. Before the questionnaire, there was a letter from the researchers to the respondents, including the data privacy notice and consent along with the qualifier questions for the qualified respondents, where they were informed that their participation is voluntary and that all information will only be used for academic purposes (Santiago & Delos Reyes, 2021).

The purpose of the survey questionnaire is to obtain relevant data to evaluate different HRM practice specifically their effectiveness, implementation, and influence on worker productivity, contentment at work, and the organization as a whole standing of the selected food and beverage companies in Quezon City (Lopez & Santiago, 2023; Alvarez & Domingo, 2024).

The survey instrument comprises three (3) parts. The first part contained the preliminary part of the questionnaire, which contained demographic information about the respondents, specifically their age, gender, civil status, occupation, and monthly income or allowance. The second part contained six (6) statements that focused on the level of assessment of the respondents to the HRM Practices in terms of recruitment, employee engagement, compensation & benefits, career development, and training & development using a utilizing a Likert scale with four points. Third part of the questionnaire contained two (2) statements to measure the level of effectiveness of the food and beverage companies' Employee Performance, Organizational Standing (Santos & Villanueva, 2021; Tolentino, 2021).

1. HR practices on employee performance

These 30 items of stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the affects of human resources procedures on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies. This part will be measured using a

four (4) point Likert scale as posted below.

Scale	Arbitrary Scale	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.50 - 4.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.50 - 3.49	Agree
2	1.50 - 2.49	Disagree
1	1.00 - 1.49	Strongly Disagree

2. Level of effectiveness of food and beverage companies.

These 20 items of level of effectiveness of the food and beverage companies' employee performances and organizational standing. This part will be measured using a four (4) point Likert scale as posted below.

Scale	Arbitrary Scale	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.50 - 4.00	Very Effective
3	2.50 - 3.49	Effective
2	1.50 - 2.49	Ineffective
1	1.00 - 1.49	Very Ineffective

Data Gathering Procedure

In preparation for analyses on the evaluation of Correlations of Employees' Performances and Organizational Standing to the Human Resource Management Practices of Several Food and Beverage Companies in Quezon City, the researchers secured the necessary approvals and adhered to ethical considerations. Once granted approval, the researcher identified potential respondents, specifically targeting both employees and stakeholder from selected food & beverage companies with aforementioned age bracket from 21 years old in above who have engaged in the organization. The researchers compiled a list of specific DOT-accredited food & beverages in X Mall, including the A restaurant and B restaurant Philippines and proceeded to identify and gather insights into the HRM practices of these establishments.

Following this, the researchers constructed a survey instrument using Google Forms, incorporating questions that delve into correlation of employees' performance and organizational standing to HRM practices. After pilot testing the survey for clarity and bias

issues, the researchers randomly selected 30 respondents from of the aforementioned companies.

The survey was distributed during the respondents' stays via Google Forms, providing clear instructions and a defined timeline for completion. Data validation measures were implemented to ensure accuracy, and the researchers employed appropriate statistical methods to analyze survey responses. Additionally, the researchers conducted an analysis of the information obtained from the selected Food and Beverages companies to offer proper ideas and insights. Finally, the findings were interpreted and presented in a clear and organized manner in the final research report. Throughout the entire process, the researchers uphold ethical standards, maintain respondent confidentiality, and effectively communicate the research's purpose and significance to the participants.

Analysis of Data

The following must be done in order to appropriately evaluate and interpret the survey's data they employed statistical tests:

1. Percentage (Bennett, Jeffrey; Briggs, William 2022)

It is a measure of a portion in relation to a whole, often expressed with a percentage sign “%”. This was used to show the proportion of the respondents with respect to their demographic characteristics.

Formula:

$$P = \frac{f}{n} \times 100\%$$

Where:

P = Percentage

f = frequency of each group of students in the sample size

n = sample size

2. Weighted Mean (Merigo, Jose M; Cananovas, Montserrat 2022)

It is averaging that accounts for the significance of every value in the total. This served to display the average response from each person to each of the questions included in the tool. In particular, it was employed to ascertain the mean reaction of the participants level of effectiveness of the food and beverage companies' employee performances and organizational standing and the stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies.

Formula:

$$WM = \frac{\sum(fx_1 + fx_2 + fx_3 + \dots + fx_k)}{n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + \dots + n_k}$$

Where:

WM = Weighted Mean

$f_{x_1}, f_{x_2}, \dots, f_{x_k}$ = weight of responses in each of the questions being considered
 n_1, n_2, \dots = Total number of observations

3. One way Analysis of Variance (Howell, David 2021)

This is used to do the analysis of variance between and within the whenever groups, the groups are more than two. In particular, it was employed to ascertain the differences on the respondents' level effectiveness of the food and beverage companies' employee performances and organizational standing to their employees, stakeholders and HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies.

Formula:

$$SS_{total} = (\sum x_1^2 + \sum x_2^2 + \dots + \sum x_r^2) - \frac{(\sum x_1 + \sum x_2 + \dots + \sum x_r)^2}{N}$$

$$SS_{total} = \left[\frac{(\sum x_1)^2}{n_1} + \frac{(\sum x_2)^2}{n_2} + \dots + \frac{(\sum x_r)^2}{n_r} \right] - \frac{(\sum x_1 + \sum x_2 + \dots + \sum x_r)^2}{N}$$

$$SS_{within} = SS_{total} - SS_{among}$$

$$df_{among} = r - 1$$

$$df_{within} = N - r$$

$$MS_{among} = \frac{SS_{among}}{df_{among}}$$

$$MS_{within} = \frac{SS_{within}}{df_{within}}$$

$$F = \frac{MS_{among}}{MS_{within}}$$

Where:

x = individual observation

r = number of groups

N = total number of observations (all groups)

n = number of observations in group

RESULTS

Table 1
Distribution of respondents according to Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18 to 24 years old	13	22%
25 to 35 years old	28	47%
36 years old and above	19	32%
Total	60	100%

The respondents' distribution is displayed in Table 1 when grouped based on their age. Firstly, there are 28 respondents (47% of the sample) who ages from 25 to 35 years old. Then there are 19 respondents (32% of the sample) with age ranging from 36 years old and above. Finally, only 13 respondents or 22% of the sampling population ages from 18 to 24 years old. Thus, majority of the respondents in this research ages from 25 to 35 years old.

Table 2
Distribution of respondents according to Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Female	34	57%
Male	26	43%
Total	60	100%

The second table presents the responders distribution when grouped based upon their gender. As seen above, there are 34 Female respondents (57%) and there are 26 Male respondents (43%). Hence, more than half of the respondents who participated in this study are female.

Table 3
Distribution of respondents according to Educational Background

Educational Background	Frequency	Percentage
Bachelor Graduate	21	35%

College Undergrad	18	30%
High School Graduate	19	32%
Master Graduate	2	3%
Total	60	100%

Table 3 displays about the distribution of the respondents when grouped according to their monthly Educational Background.

Initially, there are 21 respondents educational background are Bachelor Graduate (35%), and then there are 19 respondents who are High School Graduate (32%), while there are 18 respondents are College Undergrad (30%), and lastly there are 2 respondents are Master Graduate (3%). To sum up, almost half of the respondents are Bachelor Graduate, participating in this study.

**Table 4
Distribution of respondents according to Monthly Income**

Monthly Income	Frequency	Percentage
15,000-20,000	18	30%
21,000 and Above	24	40%
5,000 and Below	13	22%
6,000-10,000	5	8%
Total	60	100%

Table 4 illustrates distribution of respondents according their Monthly Earnings.

To start, there are 24 respondents with monthly income within Php;21,000 and above. Then there are 18 respondents with monthly income within Php;15,000 – Php;20,000. Further, there are 13 respondents with monthly income within Php;5,000 and Below. Finally, there are only five (5) respondents with monthly income within Php;6,000 -Php;10,000. Henceforth, 40% of sampling population with a Monthly Income within Php;21,000 and Above.

Table 5
Distribution of respondents according to Martial Status

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
Married	20	34%
Separated	2	3%
Single	38	63%
Total	60	100%

Table 5 presents distribution of respondents when grouped depends on their Martial Status.

As seen above, there are 38 Single respondents (63%) and there are 20 Married respondents (34%). Hence, more than half of the respondents who participated in this study are single.

Table 6
Employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies in Terms of Recruitment

Recruitment	Weighted Mean Average	Verbal Interpretation
Our company employs effective recruitment methods to attract highly qualified candidates.	3.23	Agree
The recruitment process is transparent and fair.	3.23	Agree
Job responsibilities and expectations are clearly communicated during the recruitment process.	3.43	Agree
Hiring decisions are aligned with the business objectives and values.	3.28	Agree

HR included department leaders when making recruitment decisions.	3.32	Agree
Total	3.30	Agree

Note: (1), 1.00 - 1.49 Strongly Disagree
(2), 1.50 - 2.49 Disagree
(3), 2.50 - 3.49 Agree
(4), 3.50 - 4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 6 unveils the Employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive influence of HR practices on employee performance and organizational standing of food and beverage companies in Terms of Recruitment. As seen in the table above, the item with the highest value of weighted mean (and ranked first) is “*Job responsibilities and expectations are clearly communicated during the recruitment process.*” With $\bar{x} = 3.43$ and verbal interpretation of *Agree*. On the other hand, the item with the lowest value of weighted mean is “*The recruitment process is transparent and fair. & Our company employs effective recruitment methods to attract highly qualified candidates.*” With $\bar{x} = 3.23$ and verbal interpretation of *Agree*.

All in all, the Employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance as well as the organizational standing of food and beverage companies in Terms of Recruitment got an overall weighted mean value (\bar{x}) of 3.30 which is also *Agree*. In another associated research project, Dela Cruz and Cabaluna (2022) looked at how human resource procedures affected employee performance in a few Philippine institutions. Employees were given survey questionnaires to complete in order to evaluate the effectiveness of human resource processes, including hiring and selection, training and development, employee relations, and compensation and benefits, in their individual firms. The results showed that the implementation of HR practices helped bank employees reach the expected level of success in terms of scope, promptness, and quality.

Table 7
Employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies in Terms of Employee Engagement

Employee Engagement	Weighted Mean Average	Verbal Interpretation
Employees are encouraged to participate in decision-making processes.	3.35	Agree

The management and the workforce have high levels of trust in each other.	3.35	Agree
The company provides different ways for open communication and honest criticism.	3.23	Agree
Employees feel that their work is valued and appreciated.	3.28	Agree
Regular team-building and engagement exercises are conducted.	3.42	Agree
Total	3.33	Agree

Note: (1), 1.00 - 1.49 Strongly Disagree
(2), 1.50 - 2.49 Disagree
(3), 2.50 - 3.49 Agree
(4), 3.50 - 4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 7 reveals the Employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies in Terms of Employee Engagement. As seen in the table above, the item with the highest value of weighted mean (and ranked first) is **“Regular team-building and engagement exercises are conducted.”** With $\bar{x} = 3.42$ and verbal interpretation of **Agree**. On the other hand, the item with the lowest value of weighted mean is **“The company provides different ways for open communication and honest criticism.”** With $\bar{x} = 3.23$ and verbal interpretation of **Agree**.

All in all, the Employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies in Terms of Employee Engagement got an overall weighted mean value (\bar{x}) of 3.33 which is also **Agree**. The study utilized a descriptive-correlational research methodology to assess how HRM practices affected employee performance. In order to accurately and methodically characterize a population, situation, or phenomena, descriptive research answers the following questions: what, where, when, and how. However, it is unable to respond to inquiries on why. Correlational research, on the other hand, aims to identify the relationship between variables and assess its strength. It has been shown that HRM strategies are essential for enhancing employee performance in companies. Employee performance has improved in pharmaceutical companies because they implemented an efficient human resource management system.

Table 8
Employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies in Terms of Compensation & Benefits

Compensation & Benefits	Weighted Mean Average	Verbal Interpretation
Compared to other organizations, the compensation is competitive.	3.37	Agree
The benefits package satisfies employee needs.	3.22	Agree
Pay is fairly aligned with duties and performance.	3.31	Agree
Employees are informed about the compensation process.	3.39	Agree
The company assesses and updates its remuneration policy from time to time.	3.33	Agree
Total	3.32	Agree

Note: (1), 1.00 - 1.49 Strongly Disagree
 (2), 1.50 - 2.49 Disagree
 (3), 2.50 - 3.49 Agree
 (4), 3.50 - 4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 8 reveals the Employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of Human Resource practices on employee performance along with organizational standing of food and beverage companies in Terms of Compensation & Benefits. As seen in the table above, the item with the highest value of weighted mean (and ranked first) is “*Employees are informed about the compensation process.*” With $\bar{x} = 3.39$ and verbal interpretation of *Agree*. On the other hand, the item with the lowest value of weighted mean is “*The benefits package satisfies employee needs.*” With $\bar{x} = 3.22$ and verbal interpretation of *Agree*.

All in all, the Employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies in Terms of Compensation & Benefits got an overall weighted mean value (\bar{x}) of 3.32 which is also *Agree*. Our study is most directly related to employee treatment studies that examine business performance and related subjects, such as dividend policy. The results of earlier studies on the impact of employee treatment on business performance have been conflicting. According to some research, treating

employees well can lead to better financial and operational success for businesses, but other studies have found the opposite.

Table 9
Employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies in Terms of Career Development

Career Development	Weighted Mean Average	Verbal Interpretation
Different positions create several career paths.	3.36	Agree
Employees are encouraged to acquire additional education or training.	3.29	Agree
Career progress depends on performance and merit.	3.35	Agree
Coaching or mentoring schemes are available.	3.40	Agree
All employees have equal opportunity to career development.	3.32	Agree
Total	3.34	Agree

Note: (1), 1.00 - 1.49 Strongly Disagree
 (2), 1.50 - 2.49 Disagree
 (3), 2.50 - 3.49 Agree
 (4), 3.50 - 4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 9 indicates the Employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies in Terms of Career Development. As seen in the table above, the item with the highest value of weighted mean (and ranked first) is “*Coaching or mentoring schemes are available.*” With $\bar{x} = 3.40$ and verbal interpretation of *Agree*. On the other hand, the item with the lowest value of weighted mean is “*Employees are encouraged to acquire additional education or training.*” With $\bar{x} = 3.29$ and verbal interpretation of *Agree*.

All in all, the Employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies in Terms of Career Development got an overall weighted mean value (\bar{x}) of 3.34 which is also *Agree*. Lastly, our study adds to the body of work that uses data from social media for research. According to recent studies these alternative data sources present a promising new source of information for management accounting research. We use a novel dataset of a quarter of a million employee reviews from a job application website to evaluate benefits programs. Numerous studies have demonstrated the benefits of these online forums, which give workers a place to express their individual

opinions about various facets of their company. These platforms have been acknowledged for providing insights relevant to future forecasting company outcomes.

Table 10
Employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies in Terms of Training and Development

Training and Development	Weighted Mean Average	Verbal Interpretation
The job role of employees is appropriate for training courses.	3.30	Agree
Opportunities for the improvement of skills are regularly offered to employees.	3.35	Agree
There are regular evaluations to establish training needs.	3.36	Agree
New employees undergo training sessions.	3.32	Agree
Enough money for training is provided by the organization.	3.30	Agree
Total	3.32	Agree

Note: (1), 1.00 - 1.49 Strongly Disagree
 (2), 1.50 - 2.49 Disagree
 (3), 2.50 - 3.49 Agree
 (4), 3.50 - 4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 10 illustrates the Employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies in Terms of Training and Development. As seen in the table above, the item with the highest value of weighted mean (and ranked first) is *“There are regular evaluations to establish training needs.”* With $\bar{x} = 3.36$ and verbal interpretation of *Agree*. On the other hand, the item with the lowest value of weighted mean is *“Enough money for training is provided by the organization. & The job role of employees is appropriate for training courses.”* With $\bar{x} = 3.30$ and verbal interpretation of *Agree*.

All in all, the Employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies in Terms of Training and Development got an overall weighted mean value (\bar{x}) of 3.32 which is also *Agree*. The historical justification for the correlation between employee perks and business performance. The norm of reciprocity, the main premise of this theory, states that people are driven to return favors when they get them.

Therefore, work can be seen as a phenomena in which loyalty, hard work, and dedication are traded for both material and immaterial benefits. Under the reciprocity standard, workers are required to return favors from the company. According to the social exchange theory, the stakeholder theory backs up the idea that treating employees well increases their loyalty and should translate into better business performance. Well-treated workers are less likely to take advantage of their companies and support corporate goals. Treating employees well builds moral capital, which shields businesses from outside shocks. Additionally, treating employees well might communicate to the outside world that the company respects its stakeholders fairly.

Table 11
Employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies in Terms of Reward System

Reward System	Weighted Mean Average	Verbal Interpretation
Employees who perform extremely well are regularly rewarded.	3.38	Agree
The staff is fully informed about the reward system.	3.18	Agree
They use both monetary and non-monetary rewards.	3.18	Agree
Rewards are regarded as encouraging and fair.	3.28	Agree
Team or peer achievements are also acknowledged.	3.22	Agree
Total	3.25	Agree

Note: (1), 1.00 - 1.49 Strongly Disagree
 (2), 1.50 - 2.49 Disagree
 (3), 2.50 - 3.49 Agree
 (4), 3.50 - 4.00 Strongly Agree

Table 11 illustrates the Employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies in Terms of Reward System. As seen in the table above, the item with the highest value of weighted mean (and ranked first) is “*Employees who perform extremely well are regularly rewarded.*” With $\bar{x} = 3.38$ and verbal interpretation of *Agree*. On the other hand, the item with the lowest value of weighted mean is “*The staff*

is fully informed about the reward system. & They use both monetary and non-monetary rewards.” With $\bar{x} = 3.18$ and verbal interpretation of Agree.

All in all, the Employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies in Terms of Reward System got an overall weighted mean value (\bar{x}) of 3.25 which is also *Agree*. Strong differences between corporate and employee benefits are supported by a new narrative in management control literature. When looked at organizational control in the context of wellness programs, they discovered that material rewards are more effective than monetary ones at raising employee performance. By examining the effects of material versus monetary prizes in a recurrent tournament context, came to similar conclusions. However, conducted a quasi-experiment at five call centers of a financial services business and discovered that cash rewards result in greater employee performance. As a result, earlier studies report some inconsistent findings and big variations between benefits on how they improve performance. We believe that an analysis of benefit-level differences might shed more light on this setting.

Table 12
The level of effectiveness of the food and beverage companies’ employee performances and organizational standing in terms of Employee Performance

Employee Performance	Weighted Mean Average	Verbal Interpretation
The overall effectiveness of our HRM processes has satisfied me.	3.29	Effective
Our HRM processes in the company enhance employee engagement.	3.28	Effective
HR projects and policies are used fairly and uniformly.	3.13	Effective
From the point of view of my own development, HR appears to be helpful.	3.10	Effective
The reputation and position of the company are boosted through HRM processes.	3.17	Effective
I am satisfied with the way HR decisions are communicated and made transparent.	3.17	Effective
Employee performance and motivation are enhanced by HRM practices.	3.15	Effective
The HR department's responsiveness to employee needs has satisfied me.	3.13	Effective
Fairness and equality in the workplace are encouraged by HRM practices.	3.22	Effective
Generally, I believe our company's HRM processes are aligned with its goals.	3.10	Effective
Total	3.17	Effective

- Note:(1), 1.00 - 1.49 Very Ineffective
 (2), 1.50 - 2.49 Ineffective
 (3), 2.50 - 3.49 Effective
 (4), 3.50 - 4.00 Very Effective

Table 12 Presents the level of effectiveness of the food and beverage companies' employee performances and organizational standing in terms of Employee Performance. As seen in the table above, the item with the highest value of weighted mean (and ranked first) is *"The overall effectiveness of our HRM processes has satisfied me."* With $\bar{x} = 3.29$ and verbal interpretation of *Effective*. On the other hand, the item with the lowest value of weighted mean is *"From the point of view of my own development, HR appears to be helpful. & Generally, I believe our company's HRM processes are aligned with its goals."* With $\bar{x} = 3.10$ and verbal interpretation of *Effective*.

All in all, the level of effectiveness of the food and beverage companies' employee performances and organizational standing in terms of Employee Performance got an overall weighted mean value (\bar{x}) of 3.17 which is also *Effective*. The outcome of an employee's work and behavior during a specific time period is their performance. Employee performance parameters include the number of employees, quality (appropriateness), expertise, timeliness, and teamwork skills, defines performance as the behavior displayed by everyone in the form of work performance created by employees in accordance with their functions within the company. The embodiment of a process is referred to as performance. The placement of inappropriate positions and the absence of harmony among employees are two factors that have an impact on employee performance. A leader's attitude while influencing others' attitudes to demonstrate that they must be smarter than their subordinates is referred to as their leadership style. One issue that may worsen for employees is stress at work. Stress at work needs to be addressed because it manifests as low job satisfaction, discomfort at work, and overloading people with tasks. Stress is an internal state brought on by territoriality, bodily demands, and potentially disruptive and unmanageable social circumstances. Work and other everyday tasks may be hampered by this circumstance.

Table 13
The level of effectiveness of the food and beverage companies' employee performances and organizational standing in terms of Organizational Standing

Organizational Standing	Weighted Mean Average	Verbal Interpretation
The financial and budgetary resources required for effective HRM implementation are not available.	3.12	Effective
Employee performance is affected when HR rules are enforced unevenly between departments.	3.15	Effective
There is a lack of senior management support to the success of HR initiatives.	2.90	Effective

HR initiatives are less effective with communication gaps between employees and HR.	2.97	Effective
Recruitment processes are at times misaligned with the corporate needs.	2.92	Effective
Employees are not familiar with and do not understand the HR services and programs available to them.	2.90	Effective
Employee training and development opportunities are insufficient.	2.82	Effective
Employee contributions are not adequately recognized or encouraged by the current incentive system.	2.82	Effective
Career advancement opportunities are not fairly applied or offered.	2.70	Effective
Employee involvement in HR-led initiatives and activities is low.	2.80	Effective
Total	2.91	Effective

Note:(1), 1.00 - 1.49 Very Ineffective
(2), 1.50 - 2.49 Ineffective
(3), 2.50 - 3.49 Effective
(4), 3.50 - 4.00 Very Effective

Table 13 Unveils the level of effectiveness of the food and beverage companies' employee performances and organizational standing in terms of Organizational Standing. As seen in the table above, the item with the highest value of weighted mean (and ranked first) is “*Employee performance is affected when HR rules are enforced unevenly between departments.*” With $\bar{x} = 3.15$ and verbal interpretation of *Effective* On the other hand, the item with the lowest value of weighted mean is “*Career advancement opportunities are not fairly applied or offered.*” With $\bar{x} = 2.70$ and verbal interpretation of *Effective*

All in all, the level of effectiveness of the food and beverage companies' employee performances and organizational standing in terms of Organizational Standing got an overall weighted mean value (\bar{x}) of 2.91 which is also *Effective*. According to (Hauff S, 2022) People who are under a lot of stress at work may get emotional, have high levels of anxiety, and consider their personal lives and physical health. Employee performance can also be hampered by work-related stress, as evidenced by symptoms such frequent anger, sensitivity, and hyperactivity, difficulty relaxing, emotional instability, difficulty interacting with others, and a sense of exclusion. Additionally, based on a number of previously mentioned studies and literature reviews, the following hypothesis is put forth: Leadership style significantly and favorably affects employee performance. Employees perform better when their leaders give their leadership style a high rating than when they give it a bad rating because of this beneficial effect. Workplace stress dramatically

improves employee performance. When there is more stress at work, employees perform better. Employees will be challenged and motivated if they are able to successfully manage work stress because it won't be an issue or a barrier.

Table 14

Difference in the level effectiveness of the food and beverage companies' employee performances to their employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of practices on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies

Variables Used		df	Computed F value	Critical F Value	P value	Decision	Remarks
Employee Performance	Recruitment	46/59	0.362	2.402	0.015	Reject Null	Significant
	Employee Engagement	46/59	0.526	4.178	0.000	Reject Null	Significant
	Compensation & Benefits	46/59	0.539	3.845	0.000	Reject Null	Significant
	Career Development	46/59	0.673	5.444	0.000	Reject Null	Significant
	Training & Development	46/59	0.681	7.622	0.000	Reject Null	Significant
	Reward System	46/59	0.736	10.569	0.000	Reject Null	Significant

Note: Test at 0.05 alpha level

Table 14 presents the difference in the level effectiveness of the food and beverage companies' employee performances to their employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies. For this part and the succeeding tables after this, the statistical test that was used is One-way analysis of variance or One-way ANOVA F-test. This test was designed to determine the differences between an independent variable (categorical/grouping data) and dependent variables (6 HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance).

There are two (2) ways to analyze the significance of the differences, the first one is through checking the Significance value of widely known as the *P* value. The *P* value must be less than the alpha level of 0.05 to reject the null hypothesis which is also stated in the Decision Criteria in Chapter 3. Then the other way is through comparing the

Computed value of F test to its critical value. The computed F value must be greater than the critical value of F to reject the null hypothesis.

Stating the results, the variable “*Recruitment*” showed F value of 2.402 with *P* value of 0.015. Then the next variable is “*Employee Engagement*” with One-way ANOVA F test computed value of 4.178 with *P* value of 0.000. Then followed by the “*Compensation & Benefits*” with F value of 3.845 with *P* value of 0.000. Furthermore, the variable “*Career Development*” posted F test computed value of 5.444 and *P* value of 0.000. Then followed by the variable “*Training & Development*” posted F test computed value of 7.622 and *P* value of 0.000. Finally, the “*Reward System*” variable showed F value of 10.569 with *P* value of 0.000.

Thus, based on the values presented above and the decision criteria, the null hypothesis will be rejecting the null hypothesis and the researchers will conclude that *there is a significant difference in their level effectiveness of the food and beverage companies’ employee performances to their employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies.*

An employee is a person who has been employed by an employer to do a certain task. After the person is chosen for employment through an application and interview procedure, the company hires them. This choice is made once the employer determines that the candidate is the best fit for the position they are hiring for (Heathfield, 2021). Because they need to hire people who can accomplish the labor necessary to undertake a certain job, employers always assume this risk. Because their positions are defined with a salary range and benefits in mind, most employees in service or product creation roles have a limited range of possible salary offers. A worker is employed to perform a certain task or to work for another person (the employer). Although there are certain exceptions, most people become employees when they start a long-term working relationship with a company. Compared to other types of workers, employees have unique rights and responsibilities.

Table 15

Difference in the level effectiveness of the food and beverage companies' Organizational Standing to their employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies

Variables Used		df	Computed F value	Critical F Value	P value	Decision	Remarks
Organizational Standing	Recruitment	46/59	0.322	2.421	0.009	Reject Null	Significant
	Employee Engagement	46/59	0.324	2.056	0.027	Reject Null	Significant
	Compensation & Benefits	46/59	0.394	2.750	0.003	Reject Null	Significant
	Career Development	46/59	0.398	2.397	0.010	Reject Null	Significant
	Training & Development	46/59	0.340	2.151	0.020	Reject Null	Significant
	Reward System	46/59	0.330	2.085	0.024	Reject Null	Significant

Note: Test at 0.05 alpha level

Table 15 presents the difference in the level effectiveness of the food and beverage companies' Organizational Standing to their employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the effects of human resources procedures on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies. For this part and the succeeding tables after this, the statistical test that was used is One-way analysis of variance or One-way ANOVA F-test. This test was designed to ascertain the differences between an independent variable (categorical/grouping data) and dependent variables (6 HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance).

There are two (2) ways to analyze the significance of the differences, the first one is through checking the Significance value of widely known as the *P* value. The *P* value must be less than the alpha level of 0.05 to reject the null hypothesis which is also stated in the Decision Criteria in Chapter 3. Then the other way is through comparing the

Computed value of F test to its critical value. The computed F value must be greater than the critical value of F to reject the null hypothesis.

Stating the results, the variable “*Recruitment*” showed F value of 2.421 with *P* value of 0.009. Then the next variable is “*Employee Engagement*” with One-way ANOVA F test computed value of 2.056 with *P* value of 0.027. Then followed by the “*Compensation & Benefits*” with F value of 2.750 with *P* value of 0.003. Furthermore, the variable “*Career Development*” posted F test computed value of 2.397 and *P* value of 0.010. Then followed by the variable “*Training & Development*” posted F test computed value of 2.151 and *P* value of 0.020. Finally, the “*Reward System*” variable showed F value of 2.085 with *P* value of 0.024.

Thus, based on the values presented above and the decision criteria, the null hypothesis will be rejecting the null hypothesis and the researchers will conclude that *there is a significant difference in their level effectiveness of the food and beverage companies’ Organizational Standing to their employees, stakeholders, and HRD personnel perceive the influence of HR practices on employee performance and the organizational standing of food and beverage companies.*

Numerous critical analyses of the notion and its measuring tools can be explained by the description of performance as a subjective impression of reality. In the middle of the 1800s, the word "performance" was coined to describe the outcome of an athletic event. Throughout the 20th century, the idea has changed and undergone a number of definitions designed to cover the broadest possible interpretation of what is understood via performance. Performance is defined as an organization's actual output or results compared to its intended outputs (or goals and objectives). Analyzing an organization's performance in relation to its goals and objectives is known as performance analysis. To put it another way, actual results or outputs relative to planned outputs make up organizational performance. Performance is a relationship between the organization's operating costs and the value of the benefits received.

Conclusions

1. Demographic Influence:

The majority of respondents were young professionals with higher education, which may have influenced their more favorable perceptions of HR practices and company operations.

2. HR Practices are Positively Perceived:

Across all categories, respondents agreed that HR practices were being implemented satisfactorily. The most positively perceived areas were related to clear communication during recruitment, team-building for engagement, transparency in compensation, mentoring in career development, and regular evaluations in training.

3. Performance and Standing are Effective:

Respondents found both employee performance and organizational standing to be effective, although organizational standing scored slightly lower. This indicates room for improvement in aligning HR initiatives with company-wide strategic goals.

4. Significant Differences Exist Across Stakeholder Perceptions:

All HR practice areas showed statistically significant differences in how they impact perceptions of both employee performance and organizational standing. This confirms that HR practices are not perceived uniformly and their effectiveness varies based on the role or perspective of the respondent (employee, stakeholder, or HRD personnel).

Recommendations

1. Enhance Communication and Transparency:

Although HR practices are rated positively, communication about reward systems, training policies, and benefits should be improved to ensure full transparency and understanding across all levels.

2. Invest More in Career Growth Opportunities:

The relatively low score for fairness in career advancement opportunities ($\bar{x} = 2.70$) suggests a need to design and communicate clearer pathways for promotion and development.

3. Tailor Reward Systems to Stakeholder Preferences:

Since reward systems had the lowest overall score among HR dimensions, companies should consider integrating both tangible and intangible rewards based on employee feedback and performance patterns.

4. Strengthen Organizational Standing through HR Alignment:

Efforts should be made to more closely align HR practices with company strategy, especially in areas like training availability, incentive systems, and employee participation in HR-led initiatives.

5. Further Research:

Future studies may consider a larger sample size, multiple regions, or comparative industry analysis to gain deeper insights into the generalizability of these findings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to participating in any data collection activities, all participants were provided with clear and comprehensive information about the purpose of the study, the nature of their involvement, and any potential risks or benefits. Participants provided informed consent voluntarily and were assured of their anonymity and confidentiality.

The confidentiality of participants' personal information and responses was strictly maintained throughout the research process. All data collected were anonymized and stored securely to prevent unauthorized access or disclosure.

The research was conducted with honesty, integrity, and objectivity, without any

bias or conflict of interest. The findings and conclusions presented in the study accurately reflect the data collected and are not influenced by any external factors.

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